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Report on possibilities for incorporating open source CAT tool functionality into the TMT

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Abstract: This report reviews potential mechanisms to integrate a Translation Memory (TM) solution into the Translation Management Tool (TMT), allowing large international surveys to improve their translation processes and deliver quicker and better quality translations. This will include further research into integration with other external CAT tools and the development of a stand-alone Translation Memory tool to which the TMT will be connected, followed by an evaluation and implementation of various TM matching algorithms and sharing of TMT data with partners via the TM solution.

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
Centerdata	Sebastiaan Pennings	sebastiaan.pennings@centerdata.nl
Centerdata	Maurice Martens	maurice.martens@centerdata.nl

Executive Summary

SSHOC project Task 4.3 applies computer assisted translation tools in social sciences. Since several large international social science survey projects use the Translation Management Tool (TMT) to support their translation processes, an extended review was done on how various open source CAT tools can be linked to the TMT. This report describes the possibilities of integrating open source CAT tools into the Translation Management tool.

A functionality commonly utilized in CAT tool is Translation Memory (TM), which refers to a variety of methods of processing and storing translated text in the form of 'segments' and representing them at a later time, when similar texts need to be translated. Such segments are text strings that are sentences or sentence-like strings, such as headers, labels, etc. Segments are connected in source-translation pairs, where the source is the original text and translation is the translated version of this text in a certain language. By storing many of such pairs a repository of historical translation data is created which can be used to aid translation processes.

However, given the highly specialized set of translations and processes, integrating these external CAT tools and underlying TMs into TMT is not enough. The development and integration of a new open source TM solution, tailored to the field, seems a better approach for integration into the TMT translation environment. Based on this the team has defined the following steps:

Evaluation of possible integration of external CAT tools in the TMT; the team started to explore further possibilities to integrate external open-source CAT tools in the TMT will be explored with the connection achieved between the TMT and the LINDAT translation service and MyMemory developed under *SSHOC deliverable 4.7 Code for data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT software* serving as a guideline.

Development of a Translation Memory (TM) solution; initial creation of a stand-alone TM solution that will allow users to query it for translation suggestions based on input text and source and target translations as well as allow external Computer Aided Translation (CAT) tools to query it for translation suggestions and add new data via an API.

Connecting the TMT to the new TM solution and (possible) other CAT tools; extending already existing translation functionality within the **Translation Management Tool (TMT)** tool to work together with the newly created TM solution via its API and possible other CAT tools with the aim of providing translation memories to translators.

Research into pair matching and search methods; The team set up criteria to evaluate methods and algorithms for pair matching and search, including implementation and testing of several such methods, which will then be made available in the TM solution.

The sharing of TMT data with partners; using the developed TM solution and the TMT connection to export TMT data for sharing with survey partners.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
TMT	Translation Management Tool
TM	Translation Memory
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (http://www.share-project.org)
ESS	European Social Survey (https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org)
EVS	European Values Study (https://europeanvaluesstudy.eu)
CAT	Computer Aided Translation
PHP	PHP: Hypertext Pre-processor. A general purpose scripting language, mainly used in the development of web applications (https://www.php.net/).
SQL	Structured Query Language. Language used for the definition and manipulation of data in relational database management.
XML	Extensible Markup Language. An open standard markup language defining a set of rules for documents that are both human- and machine-readable.
API	Application Programming Interface. A computing interface defining interaction between separate programs. APIs often allow client software to interact with server applications.
TRAPD	Translation, Review, Adjudication, Pre-testing and Documentation. Five interrelated procedures which form the framework for ESS translations and assessment (Harkness, 2003)
TMX	Translation Memory eXchange
XLIFF	XML Localisation Interchange File Format
GPLv3	GNU General Public License version 3

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1. Introduction

In SSHOC Task 4.3, Centerdata reviewed various open source solution that can be integrated in the TMT.

Under *SSHOC deliverable 4.7 Code for data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT software* it was already described how the team investigated various open-source CAT tools and developing a demo tool to illustrate how external connection to these tools could be accomplished, with the tool being implemented to connect to MyMemory, a Translations Memory solution.

Using this demo tool as a basis, it is possible to incorporate the same functionality into the TMT, this makes data from MyMemory available during translation work. Other CAT tools, especially TMs5, may be integrated in a similar way.

However, translation work for large European surveys such as SHARE, ESS and EVS requires a very specialized set of translations and processes. Many of these surveys have multiple rounds/waves in the TMT system, where each subsequent round/wave uses various items from rounds/waves before it. Translation quality is of course important, especially within each round/wave, but when using existing translations from previous waves the focus is on what was actually fielded, not necessary whether the translation was of a good enough quality. In the case of the ESS survey, which uses the TRAPD method, there are also a multitude of intermediary translation steps. These steps contain valuable translations, but only the final, fielded translation step should be presented as memory for a future round.

Furthermore, there are a number of other concerns which arise from relying on external, 3rd party systems as a way to provide data within the TMT in (close to) real time, namely **TMT system stability**, **Service availability** and **Language availability**. This will be further explained in paragraph 3.

Because of this, it is the team's opinion that while implementing a connection to systems such as MyMemory in the TMT will be a worthwhile addition to the system, it cannot fully support all the needs for the European surveys. Thus, a decision has been made to not only research the possibilities of integrating external CAT tools such as MyMemory into the TMT, but to also implement a new stand-alone TM solution which will serve the needs of the large European surveys more closely. Because the new TM solution will be developed and hosted by Centerdata, stability and availability issues can be minimized and any outages can be quickly addressed, without having to rely on external parties. It can be guaranteed it will fit the languages the surveys need. Like other TMs the new solution should be accessible as a service to other tools (including the TMT).

From this, the overall task was split into five subtasks:

Subtask 1 – Evaluation of possible integration of external CAT tools in the TMT; the team will further research possibilities to connect the TMT to external open-source CAT tools. The experience made during the development of the tool from *SSHOC D4.7 Code for data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT*

software allowed us to identify critical issues. The team evaluated two scenarios and has highlighted pros and cons with respect to the implementation.

Subtask 2 – Developing a Translation Memory (TM) solution; focusses on design and development of a stand-alone TM solution. During this the team designs and implements a data structure and accompanying data management logic, with an emphasis on allowing data exchange with external tools via generally used standards such as Translation Memory eXchange (TMX) or XML Localisation Interchange File Format (XLIFF). This includes the choice of the matching and search algorithms for the first version of the TM solution. The testing of more sophisticated matching and search algorithms is part of subtask 4.

Subtask 3 – Connecting the TMT to the new TM solution and (possible) other CAT tools ; The team started to program the connection between the TMT and newly created TM solution, using the tool's API to query and enrich the system. This will include as-you-type suggestions in the TMT interface that rely on results from the TM solution.

Subtask 4 – Further research into matching algorithms; In this part, more research is planned on other matching algorithms that could act as alternatives for the one used in subtask 2, selecting a number of them for implementation and testing.

Subtask 5 – Sharing TMT data with partners; once the TMT is connected to the TM solution and suitable algorithms for matching is implemented, data from various European projects that are currently in the TMT should be imported to the TM solution to be made available as Translation Memories and exports in the form of, for example, TMX and XLIFF files.

Translation Memory

Translation Memory (TM) refers to a variety of methods of storing translated text in the form of reusable 'segments'. Such segments are text strings that are sentences or sentence-like strings, such as headers, labels, etc. Segments are connected together in source-translation pairs, where the source is the original text and translation is the translated version of this text in a certain language. By storing many of such pairs, a repository of historical translation data is build, which can be used to aid translation processes.

TMs are used regularly in Computer Assisted Translation (CAT) and there are a number of commercial and non-commercial applications both providing and using TM.

An example of a TM is MyMemory, which is a large, publicly available source for translation memories, sourced from European Union and United Nations projects. It provides a search like lookup of translated segments for a great number of language pairs in various subject domains. It also contains translations by users of MateCat, which is an open-source CAT tool

that offers a freely accessible service to translate source documents into a variety of languages. MateCat automatically adds users' translations to MyMemory as translation memories (by default).

Translation Management Tool (TMT)

The Translation Management Tool is a web-based tool developed by Centerdata to support the translation process of large multicultural and multilingual surveys, such as SHARE, ESS, EVS and various other large international survey projects. It was developed under the GPLv3 license.

The tool is specifically designed to support the translation of questionnaires following the 'team' or 'committee approach' or TRAPD process, which is state-of-the-art in academic questionnaire translation (Harkness 2003). It splits a source questionnaire description up into related segments, such as question texts, interviewer instructions, response options and fill variables. For scripted questionnaires, it provides support to manage the translation of any software related texts, such as that of buttons, pop-up texts, etc. Translation process managers can add information such as translator instructions, action points and other annotations and upload documents to guide translators with their work. Participants in the process can communicate within the tool.

TMT is used as an integrated part of the development process of more complex questionnaires and interviewing instruments and can import and export a number of predefined formats, including (but not limited to) various XML structures, well-structured Excel files, Quest (survey development software developed by Centerdata) and Blaise (survey development software developed by Statistics Netherland) definitions.

For longitudinal studies, TMT is especially convenient, since it allows for the reuse of existing translations from previous waves/rounds that are stored in the system.

2. Evaluation of possible integration of external CAT tools in the TMT

Translation Memory (TM) tools may offer a much needed extension of functionality within the TMT, therefore, the goal of this step is to evaluate a possible expansion of functionalities of the TMT to incorporate TM functionality that is already available in other CAT tools.

Currently, connection from the TMT to the LINDAT translations service has already been achieved, which indicates that integration of other external tools may also be feasible. Furthermore, the demo tool implemented for *SSHOC Deliverable 4.7 Code for data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT software*, which connects to MyMemory, allows a user to enter a (partial) text string and source and target language to receive translated segment suggestions from MyMemory. In short, this earlier development may serve as a guideline for research into further integration possibilities.

The team will research further if and how such connections can be implemented in the TMT and what is needed to do so. This will also include a resumption of the research work already done for *SSHOC Deliverable 4.7 Code for data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT software* into possible other tools.

The concerns on the use of 3rd party services mentioned in the Introduction and expanded upon in paragraph 3, namely **TMT system stability**, **Service availability** and **Language availability**, are taken into account when evaluating all external services.

At the end of this subtask, the team will select one or more tools to incorporate into the TMT. Actual implementation of such a connection should be generalised for development purposes, and as such, actual work on implementation regarding user interface and changes to the TMT tool will be discussed as part of paragraph 4.

3. Developing a Translation Memory solution

In the introduction several reasons were described for developing a new TM solution, first and foremost being the specialized needs of large European surveys such as SHARE, ESS and EVS in terms of their translations and processes. The other more technical concerns surrounding the use of 3rd party systems can be described as following:

TMT system stability – relying on external systems means that new error conditions are introduced into the TMT, for instance due to unexpected return variables or non-response due to bugs within the external system. This may compromise TMT stability. Furthermore, external systems may be subject to change due to development. This may mean currently used functionality might break due to such updates.

Service availability – accessing external services requires the TMT to contact servers outside of its own network via the internet. When operation of the external service is normal, this should work as intended. However, there are a number of failure points which could occur at the external service over which the TMT has no control. Such failures may include DNS errors, server failures or external tool crashes.

Language availability – when a survey needs to be translated in multiple languages, the same CAT tools should be available to all languages that need to be translated, possibly even in local dialects

The TM solution will be developed to run as an independent service. It will interface with external tools. It will be implemented in such a way that it can be queried and enriched by external tools. The solution will be developed under the GPLv3 license.

The first step in this development is the design of a detailed layout in which all parts and their interactions are clearly designed. In this section four areas of development will be identified, as well as detail entities and data storage, pair matching data and logic, search considerations, the possibility of enriching the system with external data and implementation and testing procedures.

The following areas of development are defined:

Storage of Segment, Pairs and meta-data – the system stores text segments and segments pairs, along with needed meta information such as origin, authorship, etc. Connection to meta data needs to be implemented in such a way that new types of meta data can be added as needed.

Management Interface – A simple management interface needs to be developed to visualize and manage stored data. The specifics of such an interface are to be determined once the core design of the system is finalized but will likely be based directly on Data entities (see paragraph 3.1).

Client Interface – A simple client interface needs to be implemented to allow direct querying of the system by typing a text string, and choosing a source and target language, after which users will be presented with suggestions from the system.

Web API – the system implements a web API which can be used by external tools to communicate with the system. This should allow external systems to: 1) search the TM database (see paragraph 3.3); 2) add new segments/pairs (see paragraph 3.4); 3) export data in various standards, such as TMX and XLIFF.

For the three latter areas, a rudimentary user management system should also be designed in order to properly handle access to the system.

3.1. Entities and data storage

The TM solution is designed using Object Oriented programming and data is defined in the form of entities. Each entity can be seen as a schema for a part of the data, as well as class definitions for the programmed objects. The following is a short explanation of these entities. Please note that implementation may require the creation of additional entities and that what is described here may still be subject to change.

FIGURE 1 - (SIMPLIFIED) OVERVIEW OF DATA ENTITIES

Data directly related to segments and pairs are handled primarily by the following entities:

Segment – this entity contains actual segment information, meaning 1) a text string; 2) reference to the locale; 3) reference to the primary author; 4) reference to the origin.

SegmentPair – this entity includes pair information (see next paragraph), including: 1) reference to the segments; 2) Some way of indicating match quality.

Locale – this entity holds information related to a locale, including a reference to language, region/country and locale codes (i.e. de-DE, fr-BE, etc).

This is accompanied by a variety of meta-data entities, which could be used as filter parameters for searching (see paragraph 2.3):

Author – an author, identified by name.

Origin – the origin of the Segment. This primarily is a name formatted in a specific way: “<survey>/<wave>” or “<project>/<subproject>”.

Region – a language region or country, such as Germany or France. Should be extensible to include more meta-data on a region when necessary

Language – a language, such as Italian or Spanish.

3.2. Pair matching

A TM solution should store segments efficiently in a way that allows for the creation of pairs or “translation units” (Simard, 2020). For the development, the team will use the term “pairs”. In the last paragraph, a number of entities were defined which will store the data and provide related logic, primarily “Segment” to store the actual text strings and related locale data via the “Locale” entity, and “SegmentPair” to store pairing information.

The creation of pairs could be done in a variety of ways. Initially, the team focusses on the following:

Input segments sharing source text – one advantage of importing data from external systems like the Translation Management Tool (TMT) is that these often have extra information which can be used in the matching process. In the TMT for instance each segment has an English source version that is inherently connected to all translated versions, meaning this can be used as a direct basis for creating pairs.

New pairs through segment-by-segment comparison – If there are already pairs in the system, it may be possible to create new pairs by comparing segments of the same locale and using existing pairs for those segments to create new ones.

Initially, a default matching method will be decided upon and implemented which will be detailed in further reports. Pair quality and efficiency will not be heavily considered for during the initial development. This will be a focus of subtask 4, which will be explained in paragraph 5.

3.3. Searching

The aim of TM solutions is to provide historical translation data to help with the translation process. This can only be accomplished if users or external systems have a way to properly query the system. In other words, a search functionality must also be implemented.

Search functionality within a TM solution shares many of the challenges that have already been discussed in the previous paragraph on pair matching and may in fact build upon the same methods. However, unlike matching pairs, any search functionality will need to be efficient and responsive because it will likely be used directly by users or external systems.

FIGURE 2 - AN EXTERNAL CAT TOOL QUERIES THE TM SOLUTION VIA ITS API

A primary goal for a search functionality in the TM solution is that it can be used to serve up suggestions quickly, with a minimum input of: 1) a text string; 2) a source locale (i.e. the locale of the sent string); 3) a target locale (i.e. the language for the resulting suggestions).

The following are some querying scenarios that the team reviewed:

Using source text – A translator is starting work in an external CAT tool. The external tool then sends the source text (for instance English) to the TM solution. The TM solution will then do a search and return a number of suggested translations, which can then be presented to the user in the external CAT tool.

Using translator input – Again, a translator is working in an external CAT tool which will query the TM solution. However, in this scenario, the input text is what the translator is currently typing. In this

scenario, requests are done on an as-you-type basis, meaning that a far larger volume of queries should be expected. Speed of the search algorithm is more of a concern here.

Although at a minimum three input parameters are needed, further filtering parameters should be considered to allow for more specific needs, especially in terms of search scope. Consider the following (non-exhaustive) list of possible scopes a user might want:

- **Private** – memories created through the work of an individual user and generally only used by them (See also *SSHOC Deliverable 4.9 Guidelines on the use of Translation Memories in survey translations*).
- **Translation/version** – memories created within a translation/version, for instance “German (Germany) – verification”, where German is the language version, Germany is the country, and verification is the quality assurance step in the questionnaire translation process. Available to all users working on that translation.
- **Language** – memories within a specific language, for instance Italian (Italy), available when working on that language.
- **Shared Language** – memories within a shared language (for instance Italian in Italy and Switzerland), available when working on that shared language.
- **Wave/round** – memories created within a previous round or wave of a survey, available to all within that wave/round.
- **Global** – all memories in the tool, regardless of origin.

For such filtering, entities holding the meta data, such as “Author” and “Origin”, could be used. Such data should also be visible to users/translators to allow them to make a decision on whether or not to use a TM suggestion or not.

Having defined the requirements for a search functionality the primary challenge will be to find algorithms which are efficient enough to do this for the PHP/SQL based tool. As with pair matching, research into specific search methods are handled in subtask 4 (see paragraph 5).

3.4. Enriching the system with external data

The TM solution should also be able to receive new segments and (possible) pairing information from external sources. Import of such information should be possible in a variety of ways:

Via direct import via the management interface – here, data is added to the TM database via an import function that is available in the management interface. In this scenario, data is uploaded to the system via a file, such as a TMX, XLIFF or TMT standard XML export file which exports translations paired with a source text. The advantage of this method is that it is easier to control new input into the system as each upload is done only by a user with management access. Furthermore, files such as the TMT standard XML export can contain large sets of segments that are all paired in the same way. However, a

downside of this method is that it excludes non-manager users from adding to the TM database, which would prevent creation of private TMs.

Via the web API – here, data is added to the TM database via API functions that are directly available to connected external services, such as the TMT, allowing new segments and pairs to be added individually. If properly integrated into the external service, an advantage of this approach would be that it allows users of those systems to add new data to the TM database as they are translating, thus allowing them to create private TMs. However, because additions consist of isolated pairs and segments, guaranteeing overall consistency between newly added pieces of data will become more difficult.

A combination of both approaches is necessary to allow for both the import of larger data sets and flexible addition for the purpose of private TMs.

3.5. Implementation and testing

The tool could be implemented using PHP as a programming language and SQL database. It is possible that during the implementation of the tool, feedback loops back to the design phase will lead to fine tuning of the tool. The team plans to document this in future reports.

A testing procedure is still to be decided upon, but should depend on the following criteria:

- 1) Ability to assess the functionalities in regards to performance.
- 2) Ability to evaluate the quality of the result provided.

Failure to identify issues regarding these two criteria could result in suboptimal outcomes. For the first criterion, issues could affect user experience negatively: high latency or inconsistency in terms of values returned by the TM solution could slow down a translator's work as they have to wait on the service to return results before being able to continue. For the second criterion, issues could have an adverse effect on the quality of translation, with bad suggestions possibly leading to a decrease in overall translation quality.

Testing should minimally include evaluation via the tool's own client interface. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, the TM solution will initially be populated with data from TMT and this data will be used in testing.

4. Connecting the TMT to the new TM solution and (possible) other CAT tools

The previous chapter described the design/layout of a Translation Memory tool that runs as a stand-alone system. This chapter describes how external tools can query the TM solution via the internet. That is instrumental for connecting TMT to the TM solution in [Figure 2](#).

However, another large part was the implementation of a web API that allows external tools to query the TM solution via the internet. Because the intention is to use data from TMT to initially feed the system, a logical next step would be to connect it to the TM solution as described in [Figure 2](#).

The TMT is a large system aimed at managing translation processes. Because of this, it has a multitude of functionalities such as imports, exports, process overviews, user management and task assignment, quality checking, messaging and notifications systems, templating options, and of course a translator interface in which items can be translated, commented upon and given various statuses to indicate the readiness of the translation.

Because the main focus is to connect TMT to the TM solution and possible other CAT tools, description of the TMT interface will be limited to the translation screen.

4.1. Extending the interface with TM suggestions

In the TMT translators work on their translations in the *translation screen*. This is an overview page showing items that should be translated. During the translation process, translators can filter the items on modules and statuses. The module filter allows concentrating the translation only on a subset of all items. The status filter allows selecting items with a specific status that was set by a translator or manager or quality assurance person (e.g. verifier) in advance. Because the TMT allows users to view multiple languages at once, they can also filter which languages they want to see side-by-side. This is illustrated in [Figure 3](#).

The screenshot displays the TMT Translation Screen for Section_DN1. The interface includes a top navigation bar with 'SHAREw9', 'Translations', 'Modules', 'Status', and 'Navigate' menus, along with a search bar and 'Actions', 'Export', and 'SHARE' buttons. The user is logged in as Sebastian Pennings.

Three items are listed in the DN1 module:

- DN042_Gender:** SOURCE - English (Generic) with observation text: "Note sex of respondent from observation (ask if unsure)". Options: 1. Male, 2. Female. Translations: German (Switzerland) "BEOBACHTUNG: Vermerken Sie das beobachtete Geschlecht der befragten Person (bei Unsicherheit nachfragen). Options: 1. Männlich, 2. Weiblich." Italian (Switzerland) "OSSERVAZIONE: Indicare il sesso della persona intervistata (chiedere in caso di dubbio). Options: 1. Maschio, 2. Femmina."
- DN043_BirthConf:** SOURCE - English (Generic) with question: "Can I just confirm? You were born in [FLMonthFill] [FLYearFill] ?". Options: 1. Yes, 5. No. Translations: German (Switzerland) "Lassen Sie mich das zur Sicherheit noch einmal wiederholen. Sie sind im [FLMonthFill] [FLYearFill] geboren? Options: 1. Ja, 5. Nein." Italian (Switzerland) "Posso confermare? Lei è nato/a nel mese di [FLMonthFill] del [FLYearFill] ? Options: 1. Sì, 5. No."
- DN002_MoBirth:** SOURCE - English (Generic) with question: "MONTH:". Options: 1. January, 2. February, 3. March, 4. April, 5. May, 6. June, 7. July, 8. August, 9. September, 10. October, 11. November, 12. December. Translations: German (Switzerland) and Italian (Switzerland) are present but not fully visible.

FIGURE 3 – THE TMT TRANSLATION SCREEN, SHOWING 3 ITEMS IN THE DN1 MODULE FROM SHARE WAVE 9 AND THEIR SOURCE TEXT AND GERMAN AND ITALIAN TRANSLATIONS FROM SWITZERLAND

Translators can then choose to edit a specific item by clicking on the edit button at the top right side of the blue translation box, which will open an edit panel where they can subsequently input their translations (Figure 4).

DN042_Gender

SOURCE - English (Generic)

OBSERVATION
 Note sex of respondent from observation (ask if unsure)
 1. Male 2. Female

German (Switzerland)

Item has a locked status. However, because your role is 'Admin' you can still edit the item.

Text elements

OBSERVATION	BEOBACHTUNG
Note sex of respondent from observation (ask if unsure)	Vermerken Sie das beobachtete Geschlecht der befragten Person (bei Unsicherheit nachfragen)

MALE OR FEMALE

Response options "TMaleFem"

German (Switzerland)

1. Männlich
 2. Weiblich

Save as Cancel

FIGURE 4 - TRANSLATION EDIT PANEL FOR ITEM DN042, SHOWING TWO TRANSLATABLE TEXTS AND A SEPARATE RESPONSE OPTIONS ITEM TMALEFEM

It is in this edit panel where most of the changes to the user interface will be implemented. As mentioned in paragraph 3.3, the two querying methods: 1) using source text and 2) using translator input, should be considered.

Using source text – Because the source texts are immediately available once a questionnaire has been imported to the TMT, retrieving suggestions from the TM solution could be done at various points. For instance, the TM solution could be queried when a user clicks the edit button and showing the suggestions for each text. A different approach would be to run a full batch of queries for all translatable texts before translation even starts, which would reduce latency but would require some form of caching within the TMT. These options will be considered from a user perspective, meaning low latency is preferable.

Using translator input – Allowing suggestions to be made on the basis of input by the translator would require new functionality that is triggered by the edit field in which the translator works. To keep the volume of queries within an acceptable range such queries will be done only once the translator types a

space or is not typing for a set amount of time. The former criterium is meant to ensure queries are done with completed word where possible, the latter is to ensure a query is run in times when a user is thinking about what to type next or is done typing a full text.

Another functionality that should be implemented is a way to **select a service**. Because the stand-alone TM solution is not the only tool being used, but also (possible) other external CAT tools and the already existing connection to the LINDAT translation service, the team will need to provide a way for users to select which service they want to receive data from.

4.2. Enriching the TM solution with TMT translations

Translations made by translators in the TMT can be used to add segments to the TM solution, as well as automatically create new pairs because as was explained in paragraph 3.2, the TMT structures data so that input segments are sharing the same source text, meaning pairings can be based on that.

This enrichment could be done at a variety of points: at the end of a round/wave of a survey, at certain TRAPD steps, after a full item has been translated, etc. In terms of practical implementation, it does not really matter at which point this happens.

However, the main challenge the team faces here is how to determine translation quality. During the translation process, each text segment can go through multiple versions before arriving at an accepted or signed-off version. This means that not all versions of the translation will be of a good enough quality to warrant inclusion into the TM solution.

It should be carefully considered how the TMT is used in various projects and at which points it should be allowed to add translations to the TM solution. One option is to only allow final/signed-off translations to be added, but that would preclude using the TM solution for “personal” translation memories, i.e. translations a specific translator has done that may or may not be signed-off.

4.3. Incorporating external open-source CAT tools

In paragraph 2 research into the possibilities of incorporating external open-source CAT tools into the TMT is described. As implementation will require changes to the user interface and the development of new background functionalities much like was already discussed in the paragraphs 4.1 and 4.2, namely:

- External service specific calls triggered by:
 - the event that an edit panel is opened (when using source text as input)
 - the event that a translator is typing their translation (when using translator input)
- External service specific functions to handle return data from those service in order to present suggestions in the TMT interface in a consistent manner.

From a development perspective the resulting code needs to be manageable and as such, connection to any external CAT tool should be implemented in a generalized way, as described in paragraphs 4.1 and 4.2.

4.4. Implementation and testing

Implementation of the functionality will be done using the technologies in which the TMT has been developed, namely PHP, MySQL and JavaScript (jQuery) and CSS.

The TMT is used by several large European projects, such as SHARE and ESS. Translation Memory has been especially requested by translators that are part of the latter project. Testing of the connection could be done in the form of user testing within these projects.

Who exactly should test, what should be tested and how tests should be performed and evaluated is something that needs to be discussed with the respective parties, but currently, two types of testing could be considered:

- **Performance testing** – In this type of test the focus is on the performance of the integrated features in terms of responsiveness, latency, quality of suggestions and other points on which TM systems are evaluated. Testing could be done partially by the team, partially by people with knowledge on TM systems and would ideally have results that can be compared to existing systems.
- **Usability testing** – In this type of test the focus is on user experience. While responsiveness, latency and suggestion quality are still important, here the focus will be more on usability aspects of the implementation. This means involving end users (i.e. translators using the TMT) during translation work and asking them to evaluate the new features by means of an evaluation form or questionnaire.

5. Further research into matching algorithms

Paragraph 2 discussed the creation of the TM solution and explained that various methods for pair matching and search exist. However, the team decided to not do a full review of available methods as part of the implementation but rather implement the system in such a way that it allows us to extend and swap around matching methods.

In this subtask the various methods available will be researched, a number of which will be selected for implementation and testing. For each method, the team will explain reasons for selection or non-selection and set up a separate running version of the TM solution. Each TM solution will be set up with the same initial segment data from the TMT.

5.1. Implementation and testing

As part of the TM solution, each matching algorithm will be implemented using the same technology already used in its implementation, unless there is sufficient reason to deviate from this. If so, this will be documented.

The exact testing procedure and focus is still to be decided upon, as is the way in which the team will evaluate performance, but there are several areas that could be the focus of testing:

- **Pair creation** – focussing on the speed with which new pairs can be created from existing segments and the number of pairs that can be generated by the algorithm.
- **Pair quality** – determining the quality of the pairs that are created by the algorithm. This is a complex test as what constitutes quality is not straightforward. This may require a very strict (perhaps externally provided) data set that can serve as a ground truth and the selection of a testing methodology also used for other TM systems.
- **Search performance** – evaluation of the speed with which each algorithm is able to return search queries and how well it is able to handle large query volumes.
- **End user testing** – allowing end users (i.e. translators in the TMT) to evaluate each algorithm as they are working. This may be difficult to achieve, as it would require detailed evaluation forms or questionnaires for each algorithm and the cooperation of end users, for whom such testing would likely be considered extra work outside of specified tasks.

6. Sharing TMT data with partners

Once the Translation Memory (TM) tool has been developed and the subsequent connection of the TMT to it works, data from TM data can now be shared with partners via this connection. The choice of which data requires

- the involvement of different stakeholders
- Agreement about the quality of the data (see 4.2)

The initial pool of datasets is made of:

- SHARE
- ESS

These datasets are stored in the TM database of the new TM solution and tokenized in order to be used in any TM solution. As was discussed in paragraph 4.2, there are several quality considerations that need to be resolved in order to properly do this.

However, there are several sets of data that have been finalized that can be used. The following is a non-exhaustive list of such sets:

SHARE – for SHARE, there is a multitude of data from waves that have already finished. Translations from these completed waves could be directly used in the TM database.

ESS – for round 10, an extra effort is being made to end the process with a verified “final” translation for the TRAPD process. For each language, translations from this step could be used in the TM database.

It has not yet been decided upon which sets of data should be included. This should be discussed, keeping in mind the translation quality concerns mentioned in paragraph 4.2.

7. Conclusion

What has been described in this document is an extensive, multi-part task that includes evaluation of the usage of external CAT tools in TMT, the implementation proposal/concept design of a new TM solution, the connection of an external tool to it, the evaluation and extension of the algorithms used by it and the sharing of the TMT data via the TM solution with partners.

From this work a number of conclusions can be drawn.

Integration of external CAT tools in the TMT is possible as was also described in *SSHOC D4.7 Code for data exchange between TMT and open-source CAT software*. Further integration of external tools would benefit translators working within TMT as it would provide them with access to external sources. Conversely, the work of translators within TMT could be used to enrich these external services as well.

Translation work for large European surveys such as SHARE, ESS and EVS requires a very specialized set of translations and processes. Further concerns about TMT system stability, service availability and language availability lead the team to conclude that a stand-alone Translation Memory (TM) solution that more closely adheres to these needs should be built.

The selection of a suitable algorithm for the creation of segment pairs and search queries is a critical concern in the development of the TM solution, as it determines performance in terms of latency and the quality of responses to queries.

Finally, the creation of a stand-alone TM solution which integrates with the TMT will allow for a more streamlined and standardized way of sharing data from the TMT, both via the TM solution's API and standard file formats such as TMX and XLIFF, which opens up further possibilities for integration with other tools.

8. References

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